

NGI EXPLORERS CERTIFICATE

AWARDED TO

ERMA PERENDA

In recognition for your participation in the Next Generation Internet Explorers Programme with your Awarded Project:

RF Spectrum Deep Insight

in collaboration with

Award category

BEST PROJECT EXCELLENCE

I. STEFANIK, Project Coordinator

18 MAY 2021

Date

FUNDED BY

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 825183

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INNOVATION

NGI EXPLORERS CERTIFICATE

AWARDED TO

DR. MARTIN SERRANO

In recognition for your participation in the Next Generation Internet Explorers Programme with your Awarded Project:

Scale-Up KPI Explorer

in collaboration with

Award category

BEST NGI EXPLORER IMPACT

I. STEFANIK, Project Coordinator

18 MAY 2021

Date

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INNOVATION

NGI EXPLORERS CERTIFICATE

AWARDED TO

IÑAKI EGUIA

In recognition for your participation in the Next Generation Internet Explorers Programme with your Awarded Project:

VES - Virtual Ecosystem for Safety & Security

in collaboration with

Award category

BRIGHTEST EU EXPLORER

I. STEFANIK, Project Coordinator

18 MAY 2021

Date

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BY

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INNOVATION

NGI EXPLORERS CERTIFICATE

AWARDED TO

DR. SELVAKUMAR RAMACHANDRAN

In recognition for your participation in the Next Generation Internet Explorers Programme with your Awarded Project:

Evaluation and identifying challenges of Eyemmersive® for live and on-demand VR tours using 5G technologies

in collaboration with

Award category

BEST SOCIAL INNOVATION IMPACT

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "I. Stefanik".

I. STEFANIK, Project Coordinator

18 MAY 2021

Date

NGI EXPLORERS CERTIFICATE

AWARDED TO

MICHAL KEDZIORA

In recognition for your participation in the Next Generation Internet Explorers Programme with your Awarded Project:

New methods and algorithms for increasing Cybersecurity in Blockchain Technology

in collaboration with

EMBRY-RIDDLE
Aeronautical University

Award category

BEST EU-US COLLABORATION

I. STEFANIK, Project Coordinator

18 MAY 2021

Date

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